

Research Article

Qualitative Phytochemical Investigation of Azadirachta Indica Leaves Using Standard Extraction Techniques

Mudit Kumar*¹, Ranjeet Kumar², Yogesh Yadav¹

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Uttar Pradesh University of Medical Sciences, Saifai, Etawah 206130, UP, India

²PG Scholar, Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Uttar Pradesh University of Medical Sciences, Saifai, Etawah 206130, UP, India

The phytochemical screening of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) leaf extracts made with ethanolic and aqueous solvents is the main focus of this investigation. The well-known medical herb neem has a variety of pharmacological properties, including immunomodulatory, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant actions. Fresh leaves were gathered, pulverized, shade-dried, and then extracted using Soxhlet. Alkaloids, carbohydrates, glycosides, flavonoids, phenolics, proteins, and saponins were among the bioactive components that were qualitatively examined in the extracted materials. Standard phytochemical assays were carried out, including the Mayer, Dragendorff, Molisch, Shinoda, and ferric chloride tests. The findings showed that both extracts included significant secondary metabolites, with minor differences based on the solvent utilized. While aqueous extract demonstrated superior detection of saponins and carbohydrates, ethanolic extract shown a significant presence of flavonoids and phenolics. These results demonstrate neem's potential as a source of therapeutic compounds and validate its traditional medical use.

Keywords: *Azadirachta indica* (Neem), Phytochemical Screening, Soxhlet Extraction, Ethanolic and Aqueous Extracts.

INTRODUCTION

Azadirachta indica, another name for neem, is a naturally occurring herb that comes from the neem tree. The extract is made from the seeds of the tree and has numerous traditional uses. Neem is well recognized for its insecticidal and pesticidal properties, though it is also utilized in hair and dental treatments. In the past, fever, infections, inflammation, skin disorders, and dental problems have all been treated with the leaves, blossoms, seeds, fruits, roots, and bark of the neem tree. The medicinal use of neem leaf, in particular, have been documented. Neem leaf and its constituents have been demonstrated to possess immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, antihyperglycemic, antiulcer, antimalarial, antifungal, antibacterial, antiviral, antioxidant, antimutagenic, and anticarcinogenic

properties [1]. Neem is a fast-growing perennial tree that ranges in size from 10 to 15 meters. It needs minimal yearly rainfall (400–800 mm) and grows well in regions with temperatures as high as 48–50 °C. The plant also grows well in poor, degraded, or mined soils. However, growth is impacted by frosts and low temperatures (poor growth below 14 °C). Since neem trees are the storage or repository of a wide variety of abundant bioactive secondary metabolite (BASM), they remain an ideal research topic. Since the bulk of BASM are present in the leaves and seeds, isolating or extracting the bioactive components does not need destroying the entire plant. Furthermore, because it is perennial, the annual replenishment of leaves and seeds makes whole-plant harvesting impossible. The high proportion of water-soluble chemicals in neem BASM promotes DIY extraction and usage in conventional medicine. Additionally, most of these

metabolites are biodegradable, GRAS-compliant, and environmentally benign bioactive compounds that are safe for both people and the environment [2].

Azadirachta indica tree belongs to the family **Meliaceae** which is found in abundance in tropical and semitropical regions like India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, and Nepal. The flowers are used as element tonic, and for treatments of fever and nasal polyposis. The stem bark is used for the treatment of diarrhoea and amoebic dysentery. The leaves are also used as element tonic, to stimulate gastric secretion, for treatment of fever and as insecticide. Furthermore, in Thailand, the young leaves and young flowers of Siamese neem tree are commonly consumed as a cooked vegetable. The objective of this research was to investigate the antioxidant activity of the aqueous extracts of leaves of Siamese neem tree from several extracting and drying methods including percolation, decoction, maceration, soxhlet extraction, spray drying and freeze drying [3].

Taxonomical Classification

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Subkingdom: Tracheobionta
- Division: Magnoliophyta
- Class: Eudicot
- Subclass: Rosidae
- Order: Sapindales
- Family: Meliaceae
- Genus: *Azadirachta*
- Species: *indica*

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Plant Material

Fresh leaves of *Azadirachta Indica* (Neem) were collected during the appropriate season from a specified geographical location Near Boys' Hostel-2, Paramedical Campus, Uttar Pradesh University of Medical Sciences (UPUMS), Saifai, Etawah, Uttar

Pradesh, India. The collected plant material was taxonomically authenticated by a qualified botanist from K.K.P.G. College, Etawah.

2.2. Leaf Drying & Powdering

The collected leaves were thoroughly washed with water to remove extraneous matter, shade-dried at room temperature for a period of 10–15 days, and subsequently pulverized into a coarse powder using a suitable mechanical grinder.

2.3. Preparation of Soxhlet Extraction

2.3.1. Ethanolic Extraction:

The powdered drug was separately extracted using a 253vaporator apparatus with 80% ethanol (60–80 °C; 1: 5, w/v) for 7-8 hrs. and then filtered. Ethanol was removed using a 253vaporator to yield dried leaf 80% ethanolic Soxhlet extracts [4].

2.3.2. Aqueous Extraction:

The powdered drug was separately extracted using a soxhlet apparatus with 100% Distilled Water (100 °C; 1: 5, w/v) for 5-6 hrs. and then filtered. Distilled water was removed using an evaporator to yield dried leaf Soxhlet extracts.

2.4. Phytochemical Screening of *Azadirachta indica* Extracts:

Each of the *Azadirachta indica* Extracts was subjected to phytochemical analysis for the active constituents found in the Extracts and findings were recorded as present (+) or absent (-) according to the color change.

2.4.1. Tests for alkaloids: 1 gm of plant extract was dissolved in 10 ml of Distilled water and filtered. The filtrate was used to test the presence of alkaloids.

Mayer's Test: Filtrate was treated with Mayer's reagent. Formation of yellow cream-colored precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Dragendorff's Test: Filtrate was treated with Dragendorff's reagent. Formation of reddish-brown colored precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Wagner's test: Filtrate was treated with Wagner's reagent. Formation of reddish-brown colored precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Hager's Test: Filtrates was treated with Hager's reagent. Formation of yellow colored precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

2.4.2. Tests for carbohydrates:

Molisch's test: 1 ml of extract solution was treated with few drops of Molisch's reagent in a test tube and 2ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added carefully along the sides of the test tube, formation of purple to violet color ring at the junction indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

Fehling's test: 1 ml of plant extract solution was mixed with 5 ml of fehling's solution [Equal volume of Fehling's A (Copper sulphate in distilled water) and Fehling's B (Potassium tartarate and Sodium hydroxide in distilled water) reagents are mixed] and boiled. Formation of brick red precipitate indicates the presence of reducing suger.

Benedict's test: Take the 2ml test solution with few drops of Benedict's reagent, (alkaline solution containing cupric citrate complex) and boil on water bath upon boiling, **reddish brown** precipitate forms if reducing sugars are present.

2.4.3. Tests for Glycoside:

Keller killiani's test: 2ml plant extracts was shaken with 1 ml glacial acetic acid containing a trace amount of ferric chloride. 1 ml of conc. sulphuric acids was added carefully by the side of the test tube, blue color appears in the acetic acid layer and red colour at the junction of the two liquids indicates the presence of glycosides.

2.4.4. Tests for steroids:

Salkowaski test: 2ml Plant extract in chloroform with few drops of concentrated Sulphuric acid, shake well and allow to stand for some time, red color appears in the lower layer indicates the presence of sterols and formation of yellow colored lower layer indicates the presence of triterpenoids.

2.4.5. Tests for Protein and Amino acids: 100 mg of plant extract was taken in 10 ml of water and filtered. The filtrate was used to test the presence of protein and amino acids.

Millon's test: 2 ml of filtrate was treated with 2 ml of Millon's reagent in a test tube and heated in a water bath for 5 minutes, cooled and added few dropped of NaNO₂ solution. Formation of white precipitate, which turns to red upon heating, indicating the presence of proteins and amino acids.

Ninhydrine test: Take 2 ml of filtrate extract, 0.25% Ninhydrine reagent was added in a test tube and boiled for 2 minutes. Formation of blue colour indicates the presence of amino acids.

Biuret test: 2 ml of filtrate was treated with 2 ml of 10% sodium hydroxide solution in a test tube and heated for 10 minutes. A drop of 7% copper sulphate was added in the above mixture. Formation of purplish violet colour indicates the presence of proteins.

2.4.6. Tests for phenolic:

Ferric chloride test: 2 ml of plant extract solution were allowed to react with 2 ml of 1% ferric chloride solution in test tube. Formation of greenish- black colour indicates the presence of phenolic nucleus [5].

2.4.7. Tests for flavonoids:

Shinoda test (Magnesium hydrochloride reduction test): 2 ml Plant extract, few fragments of magnesium metal were added in a test tube, followed by drop wise addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid. Formation of magenta colour indicates the presence of Flavanoids.

Alkaline reagent test: To the test solution add few drops of sodium hydroxide solution, formation of an intense yellow color which turns to colorless on addition of few drops of dilute acetic acid indicates the presence of flavonoids.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Phytochemical analysis of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) extracts

S. No.	Chemical class	Chemical test	Ethanolic extract	Aqueous Extract
1.	Alkaloids	Dragendorff's test	+	+
		Mayer's test	+	+
		Wagner's test	+	+
		Hager's tests	+	+
2.	Steroids	Salkowaski test	+	+
3.	Carbohydrate	Molish test	+	+
		Fehling's test	-	+
		Benedict's test	+	+
4.	Starch	Iodine test	-	-
5.	Glycoside	Keller-killani test	+	+
6.	Proteins	Biuret test	-	-
		Ninhydrin test	-	+
		Millon's test	-	+
7.	Flavonoids	Shinoda test	+	-
		Alkaline reagent test	+	+
8.	Phenolic	Ferric chloride test	+	—
9.	Saponins	—	-	+

Where + is Present and – is Absent

Azadirachta indica ethanolic and aqueous extracts were subjected to a preliminary phytochemical screening to determine whether or not different bioactive components were present. Alkaloids, steroids, proteins, carbohydrates, glycosides, flavonoids, phenolic substances, saponins, and starch were all detected using several standard qualitative chemical assays. The results are shown as "+" for the presence of the corresponding phytoconstituents and "-" for their lack.

1. Alkaloids

Dragendorff's, Mayer's, Wagner's, and Hager's tests were used to identify alkaloids in ethanolic and aqueous neem extracts. Alkaloidal chemicals were significantly present in both extracts, according to positive results in all four tests. Alkaloids have a wide range of pharmacological actions, including neuroprotective, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial properties.

2. Steroids

Steroids were found in both ethanolic and aqueous extracts, according to the Salkowski test. Because they have immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory qualities, steroidal chemicals are biologically

significant and may enhance neem's medicinal potential.

3. Carbohydrates

Molisch's and Benedict's tests revealed the presence of carbohydrates in both extracts. Fehling's test, however, was negative in the ethanolic extract and only positive in the aqueous extract. This implies that the aqueous extract contains more reducing sugars or that they are more soluble. Important biomolecules that produce energy, carbohydrates may also support biological processes.

4. Starch

Neem extracts did not contain starch, as evidenced by the negative results of the iodine test for starch in both ethanolic and aqueous extracts.

5. Glycosides

The presence of glycosides was confirmed using the Keller–Killiani test, which produced positive findings in both ethanolic and aqueous extracts. Glycosides are pharmacologically significant substances with antibacterial, cardioprotective, and antioxidant properties.

6. Proteins

Protein analysis showed that both extracts had negative Biuret test results, meaning there were no discernible peptide connections. However, the ethanolic extract continued to produce negative results in Ninhydrin and Millon's tests, while the aqueous extract demonstrated good findings. This implies that proteinaceous materials and amino acids are more soluble in water than in ethanol.

7. Flavonoids

Both the Shinoda test and the alkaline reagent test demonstrated the significant presence of flavonoids in the ethanolic extract. The Shinoda test was negative and the alkaline reagent test was positive in the aqueous extract. These results suggest that ethanol is a superior solvent for neem flavonoid component extraction. The neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities of flavonoids are widely recognized.

8. Phenolic Substances

The ferric chloride assay revealed phenolic chemicals in the ethanolic extract but not in the aqueous extract. Phenolic components have a major role in scavenging free radicals and are important antioxidants.

9. Saponins

The aqueous extract included saponins, while the ethanolic extract did not. This suggests that saponins have a higher water solubility. Saponins have a variety of biological functions, such as immune-boosting, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial properties.

DISCUSSION

The phytochemical analysis of neem leaf extracts indicated the existence of bioactive chemicals that are responsible for the plant's therapeutic qualities. Alkaloids, glycosides, and steroids were found in both ethanolic and aqueous extracts, suggesting that they are widely distributed in the plant matrix. Flavonoids and phenolic chemicals, which are recognized for their antioxidant action, were more prevalent in the ethanolic extract. This could be because these substances are more soluble in ethanol than in water. However, the presence of carbohydrates and saponins

in the aqueous extract indicated that it may be used to extract polar substances. Both extracts' lack of starch attests to the phytochemical composition's specificity. Most of protein and amino acids were found in the aqueous extract, demonstrating the impact of solvent polarity. These differences highlight how crucial the extraction technique is to phytochemical research. Overall, the findings support neem's status as a rich source of secondary metabolites with possible therapeutic uses and are in line with earlier research.

CONCLUSION

According to the study's findings, *Azadirachta indica* leaves are an important source of a variety of phytochemicals with substantial medicinal potential. Important bioactive components like alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and phenolic compounds were present in both ethanolic and aqueous extracts. The difference in phytochemical makeup between extracts emphasizes how important solvent choice is to the effectiveness of extraction. Antioxidant chemicals were shown to be better extracted by ethanolic extract, but polar contents such as carbohydrates and saponins were better extracted by aqueous extract. The traditional usage of neem to treat a variety of illnesses is supported by these findings. To identify and describe active chemicals, more pharmacological research and quantitative analysis are advised. The study encourages the use of neem as a natural medicinal agent and offers a scientific foundation for the creation of herbal medicines.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Thankful my sincere gratitude to Uttar Pradesh University of Medical Sciences for providing the necessary facilities to carry out this research work. I am highly thankful to my guide, Mr. Mudit Kumar, for his valuable guidance, constant encouragement, and support throughout the study.

REFERENCES

1. Uzzaman S. Pharmacological activities of neem (*Azadirachta indica*): A review. *Int J Pharmacogn Life Sci.* 2020;1(1):38–41. doi: 10.33545/27072827.2020.v1.i1a.8
2. Loganathan T, Barathinivas A, Soorya C, Balamurugan S, Nagajothi TG, Ramya S,

- Jayakumararaj R. Physicochemical, druggable, ADMET pharmacoinformatics and therapeutic potentials of azadirachtin – a prenol lipid (triterpenoid) from seed oil extracts of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. *J Drug Deliv Ther.* 2021;11(5):33–46. doi:10.22270/jddt.v11i5.4981
3. Sithisarn P, Supabphol R, Gritsanapan W. Comparison of free radical scavenging activity of Siamese neem tree (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss var. *siamensis* Valetton) leaf extracts prepared by different methods of extraction. *Med Princ Pract.* 2006; 15:219–222. doi:10.1159/000092185
 4. Sithisarn P, Supabphol R, Gritsanapan W. Comparison of free radical scavenging activity of Siamese neem tree (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss var. *siamensis* Valetton) leaf extracts prepared by different methods of extraction. *Med Princ Pract.* 2006; 15:219–222. doi:10.1159/000092185
 5. Kokate CK, Purohit AP, Gokhale SB. Phytochemical analysis. In: *Pharmacognosy*. 34th ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan; 2004.

Cite: Mudit Kumar*, Ranjeet Kumar, Yogesh Yadav, Qualitative Phytochemical Investigation of *Azadirachta Indica* Leaves Using Standard Extraction Techniques, *Int. J. Med. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (7), 252-257. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21201855>